

Possible Neutrino Mass Spectrum above the GUT Scale

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Abstract: We consider non-renormalizable interaction term as a perturbation of the conventional neutrino mass matrix. Quantum gravitational (Planck scale) effects lead to an effective $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 Lagrangian involving neutrino and Higgs fields. On symmetry breaking, this operator gives rise to correction to the neutrino masses and mixing. The gravitational interaction $M_X = M_{pl}$ which gives rise to additional terms in neutrino mass matrix. This additional term can be considered to be perturbation of the GUT scale bimaximal neutrino mass matrix. The relation considered with solar and atmospheric neutrino oscillation data predicted above GUT scale $m'_1 \approx 0.0087\text{eV} - 0.0094\text{eV}$; $m'_2 = 0.0069\text{eV} - 0.0079$; and $m'_3 = 0.0455\text{eV}$. This is due to deviation of θ_{12} [13] due to Planck scale effects. The nature of gravitational interaction demands that the element of this perturbation matrix should be independent of flavor indices.

Keywords: Neutrino Mass Spectrum, perturbation, neutrino mass matrix

1. Introduction

The phenomenon of neutrino oscillation, impressive advance has been made to understand the phenomenology of neutrino oscillation through solar neutrino, atmospheric neutrino, reactor neutrino and accelerator neutrino experiments. These experiments enabling the determination of the Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata (MNS) lepton mixing matrix. The main physical goal in future experiment are the determination of the unknown parameter θ_{13} . In particular, the observation of δ is quite interesting from the point of view that δ related to the origin of the matter in the universe. CP violation is one of the most important problem in particle physics [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. One of the most important parameter in neutrino

physics is the magnitude of mixing angle θ_{13} and CP phase δ . The search for CP violation is great interest to various aspects of neutrino physics. At present information regarding θ_{13} , we have an upper bound that is bases on the CHOOZ experiment [6], that is $\theta_{13} < 130^\circ$ at 3 sigma. Solar and atmospheric neutrino oscillation are associated with the neutrino mass square differences $\Delta_{21} = m^2_2 - m^2_1$ and $\Delta_{31} = m^2_3 - m^2_1$ respectively. In analogy to the quark sector, θ_{12} is the e- μ mixing in the neutrino sector related to mass eigenstate as [7]

$$m^2_1 = \frac{\sin^4\theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} \tag{1}$$

$$m^2_2 = \frac{\cos^4\theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} \tag{2}$$

$$m^2_3 = \frac{\cos^4\theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} + \Delta_{32} \tag{3}$$

The numerical dependence of two neutrino masses m_1 and m_2 on the mixing angle θ_{12} . The main purpose of the paper is to study a possible relation between neutrino mixing and neutrino mass eigenstate above the GUT scale.

In Section 2, we outline the neutrino mixing parameter above GUT scale. In Section 3, numerical results are given and section 4 is devoted to the conclusions.

2. Neutrino Oscillation Parameter above GUT Scale

The neutrino mass matrix is assumed to be generated by the see saw mechanism [8, 9, 10]. We assume that the dominant part of neutrino mass matrix arise due to GUT scale operators and the lead to bi-maximal mixing. The effective gravitational interaction of neutrino with Higgs field can be expressed as $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 operator [11],

$$L_{grav} = \frac{\lambda_{\alpha\beta}}{M_{pl}} (\psi_{A\alpha} \epsilon \psi_C) C_{ab}^{-1} (\psi_{B\beta} \epsilon_{BD} \psi_D) + h.c. \tag{4}$$

Here and everywhere we use Greek indices α, β for the favor states and Latin indices i, j, k for the mass states. In the above equation $\psi_\alpha = (v_\alpha, l_\alpha)$ is the lepton doublet, $\phi = (\phi^+, \phi^0)$ is the Higgs doublet and $M_{pl} = 1.2 \times 10^{19} \text{ GeV}$ is the Planck mass λ is a 3×3 matrix in a favor space with each elements $O(1)$. The Lorentz indices $a, b = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are contracted with the charge conjugation matrix C and the $SU(2)_L$ isospin indices $A, B, C, D = 1, 2$ are contracted with $\epsilon = i\sigma_2$, $\sigma_m (m = 1, 2, 3)$ are the Pauli matrices.

After spontaneous electroweak symmetry breaking the Lagrangian in eq(3) generated additional term of neutrino mass matrix

$$L_{mass} = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} \lambda_{\alpha\beta} \nu_{\alpha} C^{-1} \nu_{\beta}, \tag{5}$$

where $v = 174 GeV$ is the *VEV* of electroweak symmetric breaking. We assume that the gravitational interaction is "flavor blind" that is $\lambda_{\alpha\beta}$ is independent of α, β indices. Thus the Planck scale contribution to the neutrino mass matrix is

$$\mu\lambda = \mu \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \tag{6}$$

where the scale μ is

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV. \tag{7}$$

We take eq(3) as perturbation to the main part of the neutrino mass matrix, that is generated by GUT dynamics. To calculate the effects of perturbation on neutrino observables. The calculation developed in an earlier paper [13]. A natural assumption is that unperturbed (0^{th} order mass matrix) M is given by

$$\mathbf{M} = U^* \text{diag}(M_i) U^\dagger, \tag{8}$$

where, $U_{\alpha i}$ is the usual mixing matrix and M_i , the neutrino masses is generated by Grand unified theory. Most of the parameter related to neutrino oscillation are known, the major expectation is given by the mixing elements U_{e3} . We adopt the usual parametrization.

$$\frac{|U_{e2}|}{|U_{e1}|} = \tan\theta_{12}, \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{|U_{\mu 3}|}{|U_{\tau 3}|} = \tan\theta_{23}, \tag{10}$$

$$|U_{e3}| = \sin\theta_{13}. \tag{11}$$

In term of the above mixing angles, the mixing matrix is

$$U = \text{diag}(e^{if_1}, e^{if_2}, e^{if_3})R(\theta_{23})\Delta R(\theta_{13})\Delta^*R(\theta_{12})\text{diag}(e^{ia_1}, e^{ia_2}, 1). \quad (12)$$

The matrix $\Delta = \text{diag}(e^{\frac{1\delta}{2}}, 1, e^{-\frac{i\delta}{2}})$ contains the Dirac phase. This leads to CP violation in neutrino oscillation a_1 and a_2 are the so called Majoring phase, which effects the neutrino less double beta decay. f_1, f_2 and f_3 are usually absorbed as a part of the definition of the charge lepton field. Planck scale effects will add other contribution to the mass matrix that gives the new mixing matrix can be written as [10]

$$U' = U(1 + i\delta\theta),$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} U_{e1} & U_{e2} & U_{e3} \\ U_{\mu1} & U_{\mu2} & U_{\mu3} \\ U_{\tau1} & U_{\tau2} & U_{\tau3} \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} U_{e2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\mu2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\tau2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Where $\delta\theta$ is a hermit ion matrix that is first order in μ [12]. The first order mass square difference $\Delta M_{ij}^2 = M_i^2 - M_j^2$, get modified [10] as

$$\Delta M_{ij}^2 = \Delta M_{ij}^2 + 2(M_i \text{Re}(m_{ii}) - M_j \text{Re}(m_{jj})), \quad (14)$$

where

$$m = \mu U^t \lambda U,$$

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV.$$

The change in the elements of the mixing matrix, which we parametrized by $\delta\theta$ [10], is given by

$$\delta\theta_{ij} = \frac{i\text{Re}(m_{jj})(M_i + M_j) - \text{Im}(m_{jj})(M_i - M_j)}{\Delta M_{ij}^2}. \quad (15)$$

The above equation determine only the off diagonal elenumerments of matrix $\delta\theta_{ij}$. The diagonal element of $\delta\theta_{ij}$ can be set to zero by phase invariance. Using Eq(13), we can calculate neutrino mixing angle due to Planck scale effects,

$$\frac{|U'_{e2}|}{|U'_{e1}|} = \tan\theta'_{12}, \tag{16}$$

$$\frac{|U'_{\mu3}|}{|U'_{\tau3}|} = \tan\theta'_{23}, \tag{17}$$

$$|U'_{e3}| = \sin\theta'_{13} \tag{18}$$

For degenerate neutrinos, $M_3 - M_1 \cong M_3 - M_2 \gg M_2 - M_1$, because $\Delta_{31} \cong \Delta_{32} \gg \Delta_{21}$. Thus, from the above set of equations, we see that U'_{e1} and U'_{e2} are much larger than U'_{e3} , $U'_{\mu3}$ and $U'_{\tau3}$. Hence we can expect much larger change in Δ_{21} [14] and θ_{12} compared to θ_{13} and θ_{23} [13]. As one can see from the above expression of mixing angle due to Planck scale effects, depends on new contribution of mixing matrix $U' = U(1+i\delta\theta)$. The above statements are not dependent on the exact form of the matrix λ given in eq(6). They hold true for any form of λ , as long as all its elements are of order 1. New contribution of mixing matrix also changes the electromagnetic properties and CP symmetry of neutrinos [18-21]. New contribution of mixing following value of neutrino mass above GUT scale using eq(1) to eq(3)

$$m_1'^2 = \frac{\sin^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} \tag{19}$$

$$m_2'^2 = \frac{\cos^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} \tag{20}$$

$$m_3'^2 = \frac{\cos^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} + \Delta'_{32} \tag{21}$$

3. Numerical Results

We assume that, just above the electroweak breaking scale, the neutrino masses are nearly degenerate and the mixing are bi maximal, with the value of the mixing angle as $\theta_{12} = \pi/4$; $\theta_{23} = \pi/4$ and $\theta_{13} = 0$. Taking the common degenerate neutrino mass to be 2 eV, which is the upper limit coming from tritium beta decay [15]. We compute the modified mixing angles using eq (13) to eq(15). We have taken $\Delta_{31} = 0.002\text{eV}^2$ [16] and $\Delta_{21} = 0.00008\text{eV}^2$ [17]. For simplicity we have set the charge lepton phases $f_1 = f_2 = f_3 = 0$. Since we have set the $\theta_{13} = 0$; the Dirac phase ζ drops out of the zeroth order mixing angle. In table-1, we list the modified neutrino mixing angles and neutrino masses for some sample value of a_1 and a_2 . Due to Planck scale effects, only θ_{12} have reasonable deviation and θ_{23} , θ_{13} deviation is very small less then 0.3° [13]. From table-1, we list the neutrino masses and mixing angle θ'_{12} bimaximal

mixing pattern $\theta_{12} = \pi/4$; $\theta_{23} = \pi/4$ and $\theta_{13} = 0$. In table-1, we have listed modified neutrino masses Vs reasonable range of Majorana phases.

Table 1: Possible value of neutrino masses and modified mixing angles for some sample of a_1 and a_2 .

Input value are $\Delta_{31} = 0.00008eV^2$; $\theta_{12} = 45^\circ$; $\theta_{23} = 45^\circ$; $\theta_{13} = 0^\circ$

a_1	a_2	θ'_{12} in degrees	m'_1	m'_2	m'_3
0°	0°	48.57	$0.0087eV$	$0.0073eV$	$0.0455eV$
0°	45°	46.87	$0.0085eV$	$0.0072eV$	$0.0045eV$
0°	90°	44.99	$0.0083eV$	$0.0069eV$	$0.045eV$
0°	135°	46.94	$0.0085eV$	$0.0071eV$	$0.0455eV$
0°	180°	48.57	$0.0087eV$	$0.0072eV$	$0.0455eV$
45°	0°	46.68	$0.0091eV$	$0.0076eV$	$0.0455eV$
45°	45°	44.96	$0.0089eV$	$0.0074eV$	$0.0455eV$
45°	90°	43.09	$0.0087eV$	$0.0073eV$	$0.0455eV$
45°	135°	45.03	$0.0089eV$	$0.0074eV$	$0.0455eV$
45°	180°	46.68	$0.0091eV$	$0.0076eV$	$0.0455eV$
90°	0°	45.00	$0.0094eV$	$0.0079eV$	$0.0456eV$
90°	45°	43.28	$0.0093eV$	$0.0077eV$	$0.0456eV$
90°	90°	41.42	$0.0091eV$	$0.0076eV$	$0.0456eV$
90°	135°	43.00	$0.0093eV$	$0.0077eV$	$0.0456eV$
90°	180°	45.00	$0.0094eV$	$0.0079eV$	$0.0456eV$
135°	0°	46.68	$0.0091eV$	$0.0076eV$	$0.0455eV$
135°	45°	44.96	$0.0089eV$	$0.0074eV$	$0.0455eV$
135°	90°	43.09	$0.0087eV$	$0.0073eV$	$0.0455eV$
135°	135°	45.03	$0.0089eV$	$0.0074eV$	$0.0455eV$
135°	180°	46.68	$0.0091eV$	$0.0076eV$	$0.0455eV$
180°	0°	48.57	$0.0087eV$	$0.0073eV$	$0.0455eV$
180°	45°	46.87	$0.0085eV$	$0.0071eV$	$0.0455eV$
180°	90°	44.99	$0.0083eV$	$0.0069eV$	$0.0455eV$
180°	135°	46.94	$0.0085eV$	$0.0071eV$	$0.0455eV$
180°	180°	48.57	$0.0087eV$	$0.0073eV$	$0.0455eV$

4. Conclusions

We assume that the main part of neutrino masses and mixing arise from GUT scale operator. We considered these to be 0th order quantities. The gravitational interaction of lepton field with SM Higgs field give rise to a $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 effective Lagrangian give originally by Weinberg [11]. On electroweak symmetry breaking this operators leads to additional mass terms. We

considered these to be perturbation of GUT scale mass terms. This model predicts the modified neutrino masses $m'_1 \simeq 0.0087\text{eV} - 0.0094\text{eV}$; $m'_2 = 0.0069\text{eV} - 0.0079$; and $m'_3 = 0.0456\text{eV}$, which corresponds to Planck scale $M_{\text{pl}} \simeq 2.0 \times 10^{19}\text{GeV}$. In addition, the solar mixing angle is predicted [12]. In this paper, we studied how physics from Planck scale effects the neutrino masses. We compute the modified neutrino mass eigenvalues due to the additional mass terms for the case of bimaximal mixing. The change in Δ_{31} , due to these Planck scale corrections are negligible. But the change in Δ'_{21} is enough that the final value falls within the experimentally accepted region [14]. This occurs, of course for degenerate neutrino mass with a common mass of about 2eV.

References

- [1] Ed. L. Wolfenstein, *CP Violation*, Elsevier Science Publishers B.V. North-Holland (1989).
- [2] L.L. Chau, *Phys. Rept.* 95(1) (1983).
- [3] J.H. Christenson, et al: *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 13 (1964): 138
- [4] E. A. Paschos and U. Turke, *Phys. Rept.* 4(1989): 145
- [5] Ed. C. Jarlskog, *CP Violation*, World Scientific Publication Co. Pte. Ltd, (1989).
- [6] CHOOZ Collaboration, *Phys. Lett. B* 4, 66(2003): 415
- [7] Harald Fritzsch and Zhi-zhong Xing, *Phys. Lett. B*, 634(2006): 514
- [8] R.N Mohapatra et al, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 44(1980): 912
- [9] S. Coleman and S. L Galshow, *Phys. Rev D*, 59(1999): 116008
- [10] F. Vissani et al, *Phys. Lett. B*, 571(2003): 209,
- [11] S. Weinberg, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 43(1979): 1566
- [12] Bipin Singh Koranga, Mohan Narayan and S. Uma Sankar, *Fizika B*, 18(2009): 219-226,
- [13] Bipin Singh Koranga, Mohan Narayan and S. Uma Sankar, *Phys. Lett. B*, 665(2008): 63
- [14] Bipin Singh Koranga, *Phys. Lett. A*, 25(2010): 2183-2188,
- [15] C. Kraus et al, *Eur. Phys. J. C*, 33 (2003).
- [16] Super-Kamiokande Collaboration, J. Hosaka et al, *Phys. Rev. D* 74(2006): 032002
- [17] KamLAND Collaboration, T. Araki et al, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 94(2008): 081801.
- [18] Bipin Singh Koranga, *Electron. J. Theor. Phys.* 7(2010): 1-6,
- [19] Bipin Singh Koranga, *Electron. J. Theor. Phys.* 5(2008): 133-140
- [20] Bipin Singh Koranga and S. Uma Sankar, *Electron. J. Theor. Phys.* 5(2009): 1-6.
- [21] Bipin Singh Koranga and M. Narayan, *Int J. Theor. Phys.* 53 (2014): 2753-2759